

INNOVATION CAPACITY OF THE ENTERPRISE AND ITS ASSESSMENT

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Abstract. *Innovation capacity. The innovation potential of enterprises in its management is revealed the need to enrich the innovation potential of enterprises.*

Keywords: *innovation activity, innovative potential, evaluation.*

Introduction:

Innovative management is a new form of management, which has entered as a form of management in demand of today's era, which is organized on the basis of modern approaches and views in management. By today's period of development, not only the development of regions and countries, industries, but also the development of enterprises directly depends on the innovative management established in them. Looking at the history of the development of the world's developed countries and corporations, we can observe that innovative activities are effectively organized at the basis of their development.

The main goal of innovative management is the effective organization of innovative activities in enterprises, and the implementation of innovative activities is carried out by forming the innovative potential of enterprises.

Research methodology

The theoretical views of researchers and scientists on the subject were studied in the research work, logical thinking, systematic approach, and comparative analysis methods were used.

Analysis and results

Innovative activity is one of the main factors in the development of the economy, and it is considered one of the priorities in the current strategic development of the state. Therefore, the need to carry out innovative activities is justified by the following.

- The transition of our republic to a new stage in the development of international trade and economic relations,
- Creation of a favorable business environment and investment environment created in the Republic,
- Strengthening the legal and regulatory basis of business and investment activities,
- The entry of foreign companies into our local markets and the expansion of the opportunity for our local manufacturing enterprises to enter the international trade markets.

The implementation of innovative activities, which is the main factor in modern management, is carried out through the formation of innovative potential. The fact that the concepts of innovative activity and innovative potential have not been brought to an essentially integrated content makes it necessary to research them. The evaluation works of different scientists based on different approaches on innovative potential and its evaluation show that there are unresolved issues on the criteria and methodology of innovative potential evaluation.

Literature analysis.

Regarding the term "innovative potential", among many foreign scientists. Scientific research works including P.Druker, Dogdson, Dafdar, Damanpour, B. Lawson, were carried out by D. Samson, J. Wozniak, R.Fathutdinov, A.Porshneva, B. Varlamov and others. In their scientific research works, innovative management, innovation and innovative authority, its structure and factors affecting it are detailed. E.A.Laptepova, O.I.Belozyorova, E.V.Zakharova, O.I.Mityakova, E.A.Yakovleva, E.A.Kozlovskaya, Yu.V.Boyko, L.N.Ustina, R.M.Sirazetdinov, E.Astashova, E. Pogrebtsova, S.Durnev have carried out their scientific research. Due to the fact that there is no universally accepted tariff for innovative potential, and the fact that it is divided into components, and the period and territory are not the same, conducting scientific work on the innovative potential of enterprises and its evaluation remains one of the urgent issues.

According to the researchers H.Danilina and N.Mingaleva, the innovative competence of the enterprise is a set of components representing the ability to create innovations and their practical use. Accordingly, innovative competence consists of components. [1]

- The human element,
- Material and technical element,
- Information element,
- Organizational element,
- Financial element,
- Element of efficiency,
- Control element,
- Legal element,
- Social element,
- Element of creativity.

According to B.A.Varlamov, the innovative competence of the enterprise is the sum of the available resources and the possibilities of readiness to use them.[2]

Above, the innovative competence of the enterprise was considered as more opportunities, as a logical continuation of it, the Russian scientist Fathutdinov gives the following tariff. The enterprise's innovation competence is a measurement tool that shows the enterprise's readiness to fulfill innovative goals and tasks, the level of its implementation, and the level of readiness to implement innovative projects. [3]

The evaluation of the innovative potential of enterprises was carried out by researchers depending on what approach the innovative potential is understood as typical. In a general sense, the innovative potential of enterprises can be evaluated based on 2 different detailed and diagnostic approaches. In the detailed assessment, the existence of the components of the innovative potential of the enterprise is assessed, while in the diagnostic assessment, the results of the innovative activity of the enterprise are evaluated.

As a result of the in-depth analysis of the scientific works of foreign and local scientists and researchers on the innovative potential, the following was formed on the innovative potential. According to the level and object of innovative potential:

- Innovative potential of the region,
- Innovative potential of the state,
- Soha and the innovative competence of the two networks,
- Innovative potential of the enterprise
- Innovative potential of the person.

Since our research work is the innovative potential of the enterprise, we present the following approach to the innovative potential of the enterprise.

The innovative potential of the enterprise is an indicator that reflects the innovative activity as a driving force of the innovative activity leading to the set goal in the implementation of the strategic development plan of the enterprise. The innovative potential of the enterprise is calculated as follows: financial and economic potential, personnel potential, production technology potential, administrative structural authority, scientific and technical potential, as well as the sum of marketing and information provision potential. Based on the above definition, the innovative potential of the enterprise can be calculated using the following formula.

$$IPE = PE_p + S_c + PT_p + MS_c + ST_p + MI_p$$

IPE- innovative potential of the enterprise,

FEP_c – Financial and economic potential,

S_c – Staff capacity,

PT_p - Production technology potential,

MS_c – Management structural capacity,

ST_p – Scientific and technical potential,

MI_p – Marketing and information provision

The innovative potential of enterprises is the central part of the overall potential of the enterprise, and it consists of the sum of the financial and economic potential, the potential of employees, the potential of production technology, the structural potential of management, the scientific and technical potential of the enterprise, as well as the potential of marketing and information provision.

Conclusion

The innovative potential of the enterprise is formed during the establishment of the enterprise. As a result of our scientific research, it was established that the initial state of the innovative potential of the enterprise IPE₀ is usually greater than 0, and during the enterprise's activity, the innovative potential of the enterprise changes due to its dynamic nature.

$$IPE_0, IPE_1, IPE_2, \dots IPE_n > 0.$$

IPE₀ - the innovative potential of the enterprise at the time of initial organization,

IPE₁ is the innovative potential of the enterprise after carrying out innovative activities for a certain period.

The innovative potential of enterprises has a dynamic nature and can change over time depending on the result of innovative activity. If the innovative potential of the enterprise is viewed from the point of view of the central part of the overall potential of the enterprise, the innovative potential of the enterprise may be smaller than or equal to the overall potential of the enterprise.

$$OP_{ent} \geq IP_{ent}$$

In this, OP_{ent} – overall potential of the enterprise,

IP_{ent} – innovative potential of the enterprise.

The innovative potential of the enterprise is considered as a part of the overall potential of the enterprise and is its central part. The innovative potential of the enterprise means that reaching its maximum level through effective management is equal to the total potential of the enterprise. Such an enterprise can be called an enterprise with optimal innovative management. This means that all the components of the innovative potential of the enterprise work at their full capacity.

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